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Kinetics of Oxidation of L-Cysteine by Quinquevalent Vanadium in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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SHRIVASTAVA and Dixit¹ reported the oxidation of L-cysteine by vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid medium and proposed a mechanism without considering the reactive species of V^V. According to them, the anion of cysteine takes part in the reaction mechanism which explains the inverse dependence of reaction on [H⁺]. No indication of the free radical formation was mentioned. In our earlier work^{2,3} on the oxidation of amino acids with V^V, we clearly observed the formation of free radicals in the course of oxidation; this, therefore, prompted us to reinvestigate the cited work.

Experimental

A stock solution of V^V was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (Reidel) in an appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid, and the solution was standardised by titrating against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator. Since the solubility of L-cysteine (NBC) in water is very low, its solution was made in sulphuric acid. The other chemicals employed in the studies were of AnalaR grade.

Kinetic studies were arranged by taking [Cysteine] and [H₂SO₄] ≫ [V^V], and the rate of the reaction was followed by titrating the unconsumed V^V in aliquot portions at different intervals with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic results can be summarised as follows and the data are listed in Table 1.

In the presence of large excess of cysteine and sulphuric acid, the reaction shows first order dependence in V^V as is evident from the linearity of

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 30°

[V ^V] × 10 ³ M	[Cysteine] × 10 ² M	[H ⁺] × 10 M	μ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
3.88	2.50	5.0	0.502	20.16	—
2.50	2.50	5.0	0.502	19.05	—
1.66	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.79	7.50
1.25	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.53	—
1.00	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.91	—
1.66	5.00	5.0	0.502	40.94	8.18
1.66	3.88	5.0	0.502	26.79	8.04
1.66	2.00	5.0	0.502	15.48	7.74
1.66	1.60	5.0	0.502	12.52	7.81
1.66	2.50	5.0	1.502	28.10	5.62
1.66	2.50	7.5	1.502	40.40	5.88
1.66	2.50	10.0	1.502	52.53	5.25
1.66	2.50	12.5	1.502	65.12	5.20
1.66	2.50	15.0	1.502	81.73	5.44

Cysteine - 10 k₂, H⁺ - 10³ k₂

log (a - x) vs time plot as well as from the constancy of the first order rate constants at different initial concentrations of oxidant. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both L-cysteine and H⁺ are found to be directly proportional to the concentration of cysteine and hydrogen ions, respectively, indicating first order dependence of the reaction on each. This is also evident from the fairly constant values of k₂ (k₁/[Cysteine] or k₁/[H⁺]) given in the last column of Table 1. The slope values of the plots of log k₁ vs log [Cysteine] (slope = 1.08) and log k₁ vs log [H⁺] (slope = 1.07) further support the first order dependence of rate on cysteine and hydrogen ion. A double reciprocal plot between k₁ and [Cysteine] with a positive intercept on Y-axis gives a kinetic evidence for the formation of complex between oxidant and cysteine.

Zucker-Hammett plot⁴, i.e. log k₁ vs H₀ and log k₁ vs log [Acid] are linear with slope value 0.66 and 0.93, respectively. A linear plot with slope value (ω) + 10.0 is obtained if drawn between log (k₁ + H₀) and log a_{H₂O}; ω value suggests the involvement of water molecule as proton abstracting agent⁵.

The effect of variation of ionic strength was studied with varying concentration of sodium sulphate at fixed concentration of the other reactants. The rate increases with increase in the ionic strength. For example, under the conditions [V^V] = 1.66 × 10⁻³ M, [cysteine] = 2.5 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ M and at 30°, the initial rate increases from 18.79 to 191.6 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹ when the [Na₂SO₄] was varied from 0 to 0.8 M. An increase in the percentage of acetic acid, i.e. decrease in dielectric constant of the medium enhances the rate of reaction. For example in 10% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid for [V^V] = 1.66 × 10⁻³ M, [cysteine] = 2.5 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 5.0 M and at 30°, k₁ = 21.76 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹, while in 50% aqueous acetic acid, k₁ = 52.52 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹. A linear plot between log k₁ and 1/D with positive slope suggests the reaction to be of ion-dipole type. Addition of NaHSO₄ at constant [H⁺]

shows an increase in the value of k_1 from 25.05 to $66.46 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at $[\text{HSO}_4^-] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, and 1.5 M , respectively. A linear dependence of rate on $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ suggests its involvement in the mechanism of the reaction. The oxidation of cysteine has been studied over the temperature range $30-45^\circ$ and the activation parameters evaluated using least-square method are as follows: $E_a = 58.68 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $A = 2.1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S = -86.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The addition of acrylonitrile effects polymerisation, suggesting that the reaction involves free radical formation and V^{V} acts as one-electron oxidant. The stoichiometry of the reaction is found to be 6 moles of V^{V} to 1 mole of cysteine. Cysteic acid is identified as the oxidation product by chromatography.

Mechanism: A number of species of V^{V} have been reported in aqueous acidic medium depending upon the concentration and nature of the acid⁶⁻⁸. In the present study, a unit dependence of rate on H^+ suggests $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2^+$ as the oxidising species of V^{V} . Further, the dependence of rate on unit concentration of HSO_4^- indicates the formation of 1:1 bisulphate- V^{V} complex as $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2 \text{HSO}_4^+$ which acts as an active oxidising species.

In cysteine the attack may occur either at the nitrogen atom or at the sulphur atom. Since sulphur is more nucleophilic than nitrogen, it may transfer electrons more easily to V^{V} which is electrophilic. This is followed by the release of protons by S-H fission from thiol group leading to the formation of intermediate complex. Later the complex suffers attack by water molecule in the rate determining step. The following mechanistic steps may be suggested,

On the above suggested steps the rate law can be derived as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K_2 K_3 [\text{Cyst}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]}{1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-] + K_2 K_3 [\text{Cyst}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{[\text{Cyst}]} \left\{ \frac{1}{k K_2 K_3 [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]} + \frac{1}{k K_3} \right\} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

A double reciprocal plot between k_{obs} and $[\text{Cysteine}]$ was obtained linear with positive intercept confirming the complex formation. Further, according to

Wells and Kuritsyn⁹, the equilibrium constant for the formation of $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2^+$ is very small and so K_2 may also be assumed to be very small and equation (6) is thus reduced to

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k K_2 K_3 [\text{Cysteine}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (8)$$

The above proposed steps and the rate law incorporates the experimental results.

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Chloride-Inhibited Chromium(VI) Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol in 90% Aqueous Acetone

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It is well understood that in dilute acid solutions, chromium(vi) is mainly in the form of the acid chromate ion¹, HCrO_4^- . In presence of anions (A^-), this species is transformed to ACrO_4^- , the oxidising capacity being dependent on the nature of the anion¹⁻³. Thus, chlorochromate, ClCrO_4^- , formed in presence of chloride ions, is a less powerful oxidant than the acid chromate ion in aqueous acetic acid. The formation of chlorochromate is substantially enhanced as the dielectric constant of the solvent decreases. The equilibrium constant of formation of this species has been shown to be 17 in water² but is very high (1.1×10^6) in 87.5% aqueous acetic acid³. The dimerisation constant of the acid chromate ion (K_d) is also largely affected by the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium. In this study, we have attempted to obtain the dimerisation constants of chromium(vi) in aqueous acetone media. We have also furnished details of the inhibition of the chromium(vi) oxidation of allyl alcohol by chloride ions in 90% acetone